

Influence of School Discipline on Academic Achievement of Public Secondary School Students' in Gombe Metropolis

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of school discipline on students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis. The population used was 23366 students out of which 355 were sampled. Simple random sampling technique was used. School discipline questionnaire was used for data collection (SDQ). Students' third term achievement scores was used to determine their academic achievement. Data was collected by the researchers and it was analyzed using SPSS version 23. Research question one and two were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. While hypothesis one was tested using Pearson product moment correlation while hypothesis two was tested using independent sample t-test. The result revealed that school discipline has no influence on students' academic achievement, it also revealed that there was no gender difference in the influence of school discipline and students' academic achievement in Gombe metropolis. The study concludes that school discipline has no influence on students' academic achievement in Gombe metropolis public senior secondary schools. It was recommended that researches should be conducted to investigate why school discipline has no influence and relationship with students' academic achievement.

Keyword: school discipline, academic achievement and secondary school students

Introduction

The problem of poor academic performance of students in Nigerian secondary schools have been of much concern to the government, parents, teachers and even students themselves. The quality of education not only depends on the teachers as reflected in the performance of their duties, but also in the effective coordination of the school environment (Ajao, 2001). The problem is so much that it has led to the widely acclaimed fallen standard of education in Gombe State and Nigeria at large. The quality of education depends on the teachers as reflected in the performance of their duties. Over time students' academic performance in both internal and external examinations had been used to determine excellence in teachers and teaching (Ajao, 2001). Teachers have been shown to have an important influence on students' academic achievement and they also play a crucial role in educational attainment because the teacher is ultimately responsible for translating policy into action and principles based on practice during interaction with the students (Afe, 2001). Both teaching and learning depends on teachers, no wonder an effective teacher has been conceptualized as one who produces desired results in the course of his duty as a teacher (Uchefuna, 2001).

Considering governments' huge investment in public education, its output in terms of quality of students have been observed to be unequal with government expenditure. Literature revealed that there are many factors that are capable of influencing students' performance, these factors include but not limited to schools' discipline, classroom management, school administrator, teachers, poor time management (Afe, 2001). School or classroom discipline may be defined as the training which produces in the learners, a life of self-restraint, orderliness, good conduct, cooperation and the habit of getting the best out of themselves. Discipline can be determined by the extent to which the learners are convinced in what they are doing and willingly submit themselves to the authority of the teacher (Anuforo, 2007). Scholars over times have written more on indiscipline among students and its effects on learning outcome and their progress in schools. One of such was that of Stanley (2014) whose study was carried out to establish the relationships between schools' discipline and students' academic performance. The study employed cross sectional research survey design in which questionnaire was the main instrument of data collection in addition to interview guide and document review. Simple percentage and Chi-square statistical method were

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used to analyze the data. However, the findings of the study clearly showed that effective school discipline should be encouraged in controlling students' behaviour thus affects students' general academic performance. Another study also is that of Pasternak and Lezion (2013) in their paper discipline, learning skills and academic achievement. The article intends to find correlation between discipline, learning skills and academic achievement. Findings from a quantitative research conducted among 143 fifth-grade students in Israel and the US indicated a significant positive correlation between four discipline skills – perseverance, meeting schedules, goal setting and planning for their achievement as well as completion of unpleasant tasks – and academic achievement. None statistically significant differences were obtained between boys and girls, between the classes tested and between Israeli as opposed to US students. Some scholars suggest that disciplinary policies simply do not have different effects (Verdugo and Glenn, 2002; Chen, 2008; Schoonover, 2009). Other asserts that suspensions do not prevent students' future misbehaviour (Nichols, 2004). If school is effectively disciplined, the academic performance on the part of student and teacher will be highly rated. Gawe, Vakalisa and Jacobs, (2001:190) express cooperative learning if academic performance is to be achieved among students. However, apart from the fact that effective discipline helps in the achievement of goals, expectation and responsibility in students (Dunham, 1984:66). Discipline creates a good image of the school and prepares learners for the future. Disruptive behaviour amongst learners is eliminated if there is good discipline at school. The implementation of effective discipline at school is a key for the student in the journey to adulthood. Parents often have no choice but to enroll their children in a school with good discipline, which often leads to better academic performances. In our secondary schools today, learners are habitual late comers; this is contrary to the school rules and regulations. They leave school premises without permission; do not bring their books to school; refuse to do their homework; reject any kind of authority and resist any disciplinary measures taken against them. Teachers on the other hand, are always absent from school; present ill-prepared lessons; fail to exercise discipline in the classroom and lack a professional work ethic. Bieketty, (2004) opined that lack of discipline and respect among teachers cause a severe barrier to effective teaching and learning in the classroom. Discipline have been underestimated by over actualizing freedom and rights, an understatement of responsibilities and obligations, marginalization of the authority of the head teacher, bad role models by some teachers, lack of punctuality, abscondment from classes by both learners and teachers and the unionist attitude of some teachers. Based on this contextual background this study investigated the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis.

Objectives of the study:

1. To find out the relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in Gombe Metropolis.
2. To determine the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of students in public secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis.
3. To determine the mean score difference between gender in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement of public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis.
4. To find out the significant gender difference in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis.

Research Questions:

1. What is the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of students in public secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis?
2. What is the mean score difference between gender in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement of public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis?

Hypotheses:

1. **H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in Gombe Metropolis.
2. **H₀₂:** There is no significant gender difference in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis.

Methodology

Survey research design was used. The population used for this study was all senior secondary students with a total number of 23, 366 spread across the 17 public senior secondary schools in the metropolis. Six schools were randomly selected also simple random sampling technique was used to select the participant using hat and draw method of drawing the participant of the study. 355 participants were used as a sample of the study. The decision of the sample size was based on the research advisor estimated sample size table. Students' third term achievement scores was used to determine their academic achievement. The instrument used for data collection was school discipline questionnaire (SDQ) with fifteen items with a five

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pint likert scale namely, strongly agrees, agree, neural, disagree and strongly disagree. This is used to register the extent of agreement or disagreement with a particular statement of an attitude, belief or judgment. The instrument has face, content and construct validity and is reliable with 0.78 cronbach alpha value coefficient. The student academic achievement was determined using average scores of students at the end of third term (promotional exams) meanwhile, all the data collected through the questionnaire were analyzed, using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Pearson product moment correlation and t-test were used in testing the hypothesis raised.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of students in public secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis?

Table 1: Result of the frequency and percentage on the influence of school discipline on students' academic achievement.

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Discipline in schools is essential for good learning	16(4.5%)	82(23.1%)	168(47.3%)	85(23.9%)	4(1.1%)
2.	Discipline is essential for good teacher relationship	2(0.6%)	1(0.3%)	3(0.8%)	59(16.6%)	290(81.7%)
3.	Student indiscipline affects their academic performance	6(1.7%)	8(2.3%)	5(1.4%)	100(28.2%)	236(66.5%)
4.	Indiscipline students in your school perform well in exams	12(3.4%)	29(8.2%)	21(5.9%)	51(14.4%)	242(68.2%)
5.	Discipline students create a conducive learning environment in schools	132(37.2%)	90(25.4%)	26(7.3%)	54(15.2%)	53(14.9%)
6.	Indiscipline students relate well with teachers	130(36.6%)	73(20.6%)	31(8.7%)	61(17.2%)	60(16.9%)
7.	Indiscipline students have ample reading time	165(46.5%)	94(26.5%)	27(7.6%)	39(11.0%)	28(7.9%)
8.	Observance of time management affects student performance	138(38.9%)	114(32.1%)	43(12.1%)	39(11.0%)	21(5.9%)
9.	School Rule and regulation influences students' academic performance positively	55(15.5%)	69(19.4%)	54(15.2%)	105(29.6%)	72(20.3%)
10.	Personality of the teacher is to be blamed for indiscipline in schools.	33(9.3%)	42(11.8%)	34(9.6%)	63(17.7%)	183(51.5%)
11.	Leadership style of the teacher accounts for indiscipline in schools	57(16.1%)	71(20%)	66(18.6%)	80(22.5%)	81(22.8%)
12.	School/ class environment is a major source of indiscipline in schools	80(22.5%)	94(26.5%)	42(11.8%)	67(18.9%)	72(20.3%)
13.	Violence affects students learning	99(27.9%)	62(17.5%)	23(6.5%)	65(18.3%)	106(29.9%)
14.	Unrests cause time wastage	49(13.8%)	26(7.3%)	25(7.0%)	61(17.2%)	194(54.6%)
15.	Indiscipline students lead a good life after schooling	40(11.3%)	50(14.1%)	40(11.3%)	77(21.7%)	148(41.7%)

Field study

Table 1 revealed that discipline in schools is not essential for good learning in Gombe State as majority 168(47.3%) were neither agree nor disagree that discipline is essential for good learning. Majority 290(81.7%) of the respondents strongly disagree that discipline is essential for good teacher relationship. Majority 236(66.5%) strongly disagree that Student indiscipline affects their academic performance.

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Indiscipline students in your school perform well in exams strongly disagree by the majority 242(68.2%) of the respondents. Majority 132(37.2%) have unanimously strongly agree that discipline students bring a conducive learning environment in schools. Majority 130(36.6%) of the respondents strongly agree that discipline students relate well with teachers in Gombe Metropolis. Majority 165(46.5%) strongly agree that discipline students have ample reading time. Majority 138(38.9%) strongly agree that observance of time management affects student performance. Majority 105(29.6%) disagree that School Rule and regulation influences students' academic performance positively. Majority 183 (51.5%) strongly disagree that Personality of the teacher is to be blamed for indiscipline in schools. Majority 80(22.8%) strongly disagree that Leadership style of the teacher accounts for indiscipline in schools. Majority 94(26.5%) agree that School/class environment is a major source of indiscipline in schools. Majority 106(29.9%) strongly disagree that Violence affects students learning. Majority 194(54.6%) strongly agree that Unrests cause time wastage. Majority 148(41.7%) strongly agree that Indiscipline students lead a good life after schooling.

Research question 2

What is the mean score difference between gender in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement of public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis?

Table 2: Result of mean difference between males and female students

Academic Performance	N	Mean	S.D	Std.Error mean
Male	97	49.57	7.20	.7314
Female	258	49.89	32.09	1.99

The result in Table 2, revealed that there is little or no gender difference in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of students in Gombe metropolis. This is because mean scores of male students is 49.57 with a standard deviation of 7.20 and the females is 49.89 with a standard deviation of 32.09. The only difference is 0.32 which is negligible.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in Gombe Metropolis

Table 3: Result of the Spearman Rank Correlation of the relationship between school discipline and students' academic performance.

Variable	N	X	S.D	r.	sig.	Decision
School discipline	355	63.69	14.036	.020	.710	Accepted
Academic performance	355	49.803	27.60			

Field study

Result in table 3, revealed that there is no significant relationship between school discipline and students' academic achievement. Spearman rank order correlation was used in testing the hypothesis. From table 3, the correlation value of $r = .020$ represents the correlation between school discipline and students' academic achievement while the sig-value of $.710$ represents the significance level. Based on the obtained correlation value ($r = .020$, $sig. = .710$, > 0.05), a statistically insignificant relationship exists between school discipline and students' academic achievement. This is because the obtained sig-value is $> .05$ level of significance. Based on the obtained result, the stated null hypothesis was accepted.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant gender difference in the responses of students on the influence of school discipline on the academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis

Table 4: Result of the independent t-test between gender and students' academic performance.

Academic Performance	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t.	P	Decision
Male	97	49.57	7.20	353	.097	.922	Accepted
Female	258	49.89	32.09				

Field study

Table 2, presents the results of the independent t-test on whether there is a significant gender difference on the influence of school discipline on their academic achievement. The result showed that $t(353) = -.097$ and $p = .922$ since the p-

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value (0.933) is greater than the alpha value (0.05), the hypothesis was therefore accepted. Thus, there was no significant gender difference on the influence of school discipline and students' academic performance in Gombe metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

This study found that school discipline has no influence on students' academic achievement, it was also revealed insignificant relationships between school discipline and students' academic achievement. It was also found that there was no significant difference between males and female students in terms of their academic achievement. With regard to influence of school discipline on students' academic achievement this study found that school discipline has no influence on students' academic achievement. This finding is contrary to the finding of Stanley (2014) who in his study found that effective school discipline influence students' academic performance. It is also not in consistent with the finding of Pasternak and Lezion (2013) who in the same study found positive correlation between school discipline and academic achievement of students. It is also contrary to the finding of Dunham (1984) who found that effective school discipline helps in the achievement goals expectation and responsibility in students. Bieketty (2004) also found that lack of discipline among teachers can affect students' academic achievement. It is not in line with the findings of Anuforo (2007) who found that there is no significant relationships between school discipline and academic achievement of students. This study found insignificant difference between gender in terms of influence of school discipline and academic achievement. The finding is consistent with the previous finding of Ajao (2001) who also found no significant difference between gender and academic achievement of students.

This finding is surprising, because previous reviewed studies found that school discipline has influence on students' academic achievement but this study found that school discipline has no influence on students' academic achievement and has no significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of students. The reason perhaps the interaction between the researcher and teachers as well as the students. It was reported indiscipline students tend to perform better than the discipline ones. It was common to found indiscipline students perform better in schools than the discipline ones. Meanwhile, discipline is different from achievement. One can be discipline but his/her performance is low and one can be indiscipline but his performance can be good. In most cases practically discipline has no relationship with an individual students' performance, however, it will be worthy of commendation when students have discipline and also perform better in school.

Conclusion

This study examined the influence of school discipline on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis. The study concluded that school discipline has no influence students' academic achievement. One being discipline has no relation with the academic achievement. It also concludes that discipline is someone behaviour while achievement is one's academic engagement to knowledge.

Recommendations

1. Researches should be conducted to investigate why school discipline has no influence on academic achievement of students. After all previous reviewed study demonstrated that school disciplined has influence on students' academic achievement.
2. Researches should be conducted to find out why there is no relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of students.
3. Researches should be conducted to investigate why there is no gender difference in terms of influence of school discipline among secondary school students.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the effort of our students' teachers who helped us to collect data in various secondary schools in Gombe Metropolis. May God reward you abundantly.

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